
IMPLEMENTATION OF A PRODUCT RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM BASED ON PYTHON AND MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

[Ciências Exatas e da Terra, Volume 28 - Edição 128/NOV 2023 SUMÁRIO / 02/12/2023](#)

REGISTRO DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10278542

Marcos Antônio de Oliveira Teixeira

Ulisses Bentes da Mota Filho

Jean Mark Lobo de Oliveira

Pablo Augusto da Paz Elleres

ABSTRACT

In the face of the digital landscape, personalization becomes crucial for success in e-commerce. This article covers the practical implementation of a product recommendation system, using Python and machine learning algorithms. Methods such as collaborative and content-based filtering stand out, with an emphasis on applications and distinct features. The agile approach, effective tools, and detailed evaluation of user interaction were instrumental in the successful development. Results indicate a significant increase in conversion rate (2.5% to 3.8%) and increase in revenue (22%). The high user approval (92%) underscores the relevance of the recommendations. Ethical considerations and

transparency in the use of data were emphasized. The article concludes by highlighting personalization as an essential strategy and points to continued adaptations and future innovations.

Keywords: E-Commerce, Personalization, Python, Collaborative Filtering.

1 INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly digital and data-driven landscape, personalizing experiences has become a crucial element for online business success (CERVO et al, 2019). In the context of e-commerce, the ability to offer personalized recommendations to users can significantly enhance customer satisfaction and, therefore, boost sales (HELLKAMP, 2020). This personalization is especially relevant in the face of the vast amount of products available, making consumer decision-making challenging. In this context, recommendation systems emerge as an effective solution, utilizing machine learning algorithms to analyze user behavior patterns and provide product suggestions tailored to individual preferences.

Implementing recommendation systems is not only a strategy to enhance the user experience, but also a strategic approach that has a direct impact on digital marketing effectiveness and conversion metrics (TURBAN, 2019). By providing personalized suggestions, businesses can increase the likelihood that users will find relevant products, promoting ongoing engagement and brand loyalty. According to Zaneti et al, (2019) the use of machine learning algorithms allows the continuous adaptation of recommendations based on the user's real-time behavior, providing a dynamic and updated approach to the personalization of suggestions. Additionally, the collection and analysis of data from the user's interaction with the recommendation system offers valuable insights into buying behavior patterns, consumer preferences, and market trends (DELANNAY, 2018). This information can be exploited to adjust marketing strategies, optimize product offerings, and improve operational efficiency. In this way, implementing a recommendation system not only directly benefits

the end-user but also provides a strategic advantage to businesses looking to remain competitive in an ever-evolving digital environment.

The article aims to present a practical approach to the implementation of a product recommendation system using the Python programming language and machine learning algorithms. Different recommendation methods, such as collaborative and content-based filtering, will be explored, highlighting their distinct applications and characteristics. The article will provide step-by-step guidance on building and training the model, integrating it with user data and products, and evaluating the effectiveness of the system. By the end, it is expected that readers will have acquired practical knowledge to implement and customize recommendation systems in their own applications, promoting improvement in user experience and effectiveness in business strategies.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Personalizing experiences in e-commerce is an essential approach to meeting the increasingly demanding expectations of consumers in a dynamic digital environment (RHEUDE, 2019). This transformative phenomenon has been driven by innovative strategies, most notably recommender systems powered by machine learning algorithms. These systems play a crucial role in analyzing the vast pool of data available, understanding users' individual preferences, purchase history, and online behavior. The ability to offer personalized recommendations not only simplifies consumer decision-making, but also reveals itself as a strategic tool in digital marketing, directly impacting the effectiveness of conversion strategies and building brand loyalty (CHEN, 2018). However, the successful implementation of personalization requires an ethical approach, balancing the delivery of engaging experiences with the security and privacy of customer data. This theoretical framework explores the intersection between personalization, recommendation systems, impact on digital marketing strategies, and the application of machine

learning algorithms, highlighting their importance in the context of contemporary e-commerce.

2.1 PERSONALIZATION OF E-COMMERCE EXPERIENCES

Personalizing e-commerce experiences has become a crucial element in satisfying growing consumer expectations in a dynamic digital environment. By tailoring interaction with users based on their individual preferences, purchase history, and online behavior, businesses can create more meaningful shopping experiences that align with customer expectations. This approach not only contributes to immediate customer satisfaction but also lays the foundation for loyalty, as consumers feel recognized and valued in their online interactions.

Among the most effective personalization strategies, personalized recommendations stand out, driven by recommendation systems powered by machine learning algorithms. These systems analyze past user behavior to suggest relevant products, providing a more targeted buying journey. Tailored special offers and discounts, personalization of pages and content, as well as personalized communications, play key roles in creating a unique shopping experience for each customer, adding value to the interaction and encouraging repeat purchases. However, while personalization offers numerous advantages, it is crucial to address ethical challenges such as customer privacy and transparency in data use. Companies must ensure ethical data collection and storage practices, while respecting user privacy and being transparent about how data is used for personalization. The balance between delivering engaging personalized experiences and ensuring data security and privacy is essential for building and maintaining customer trust in the competitive e-commerce environment.

2.2 RECOMMENDATION SYSTEMS AS A SOLUTION IN E-COMMERCE

Recommender systems emerge as innovative and fundamental solutions in the context of e-commerce, meeting the increasing complexity of

consumer decision-making in the face of a wide range of products. Given this abundance, such systems, driven by machine learning algorithms, play a crucial role in analyzing user behavior patterns. By understanding individual preferences, purchase history, and previous interactions, these systems are able to provide highly personalized suggestions, making the shopping experience more efficient, engaging, and in line with consumer expectations.

Not only does this approach simplify the choice process for consumers, but it also reveals itself as a strategic strategy for businesses, directly impacting digital marketing effectiveness and conversion metrics. By offering personalized recommendations, businesses significantly increase the likelihood that users will find relevant products, promoting not only the completion of a sale but also ongoing engagement and building brand loyalty. In this way, recommendation systems not only address the need for personalization in e-commerce, but also stand out as strategic tools that confer a competitive advantage, strengthening the connection between consumers and brands in a dynamic digital landscape.

2.3 IMPACT OF PERSONALIZATION ON DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES

The impact of personalization on digital marketing strategies is profound and transformative, reflecting the evolution of traditional approaches to engaging consumers online. By offering content and experiences tailored to users' individual preferences, personalized strategies not only capture attention but also create more meaningful emotional connections. This personalization goes further than simple name recognition, involving customizing offers, product recommendations, and even visually styling content to align with each user's specific interests.

Effective implementation of personalization in digital marketing leads to a substantial increase in perceived consumer relevance, resulting in higher engagement rates. Precise audience segmentation and delivery of

highly relevant messages not only increase the likelihood of conversion but also contribute to building brand loyalty. Continuous personalization, often powered by machine learning algorithms, allows for dynamic adaptation to changing consumer preferences and behaviors in real-time. This continuous cycle of learning and tweaking not only optimizes the effectiveness of marketing strategies but also creates a more engaging and personalized user experience, thereby solidifying the brand's presence in the competitive digital landscape. Therefore, personalization is not just a passing trend, but rather an essential strategic approach for businesses looking to establish lasting and meaningful connections with their target audience in the digital universe.

2.4 MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

Machine learning algorithms play a key role in recommender systems, boosting the ability of these systems to analyze large data sets and discern complex patterns in user behavior. These algorithms can be categorized into several types, with collaborative and content-based filtering standing out as widely used approaches. In collaborative filtering, the system analyzes the behavior of similar users, identifying patterns and suggesting items based on the preferences of others who have similar tastes. Content-based filtering, on the other hand, uses specific characteristics of the items and the user, suggesting products based on similarity to previously reviewed or purchased items. Effectively applying these algorithms not only enhances the accuracy of recommendations but also allows for continuous adaptation based on real-time user behavior, providing a dynamic and highly personalized recommendation experience in the context of e-commerce.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The approach adopted for the development of the recommender system was based on agile principles, notably using the Scrum framework. This choice was based on the need for adaptability in dynamic

projects, such as the implementation of recommender systems. The activities were structured in sprints, with an average of two weeks each, aiming at incremental and continuous delivery of features. During the planning of each sprint, priority features were identified based on user requirements, previous feedback, and business goals. The implementation was carried out in Python, a language recognized for its popularity and robustness in machine learning.

Conducting unit and integration testing was a priority, highlighting the importance of ensuring the quality and functionality of the new features, with a focus on early detection of potential issues. At the end of each sprint, a review of the implemented functionalities was conducted, including demonstrations for stakeholders. The feedback received played a crucial role, guiding ongoing adjustments and refinements. In addition, a retrospective of the sprint was conducted, identifying strengths, areas of improvement and necessary adjustments in the process. This systematic practice of evaluation and adaptation has contributed significantly to improving efficiency over time.

3.1 TOOLS USED FOR COLLABORATION AND MANAGEMENT

In order to facilitate collaboration and effective project management, a variety of tools were employed. Version control was ensured through Git, with the repository hosted on GitHub, allowing for change tracking and efficient collaboration on parallel developments. For project management, the Jira tool was instrumental, making it possible to create user stories, assign tasks, and monitor progress. The Canva platform was used in the creation of graphic material, such as system architecture diagrams. Its intuitive interface provided effective visual communication of complex concepts, making it easier for stakeholders to understand.

3.2 EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SYSTEM AND INTERACTION WITH USERS

After iterations were completed, the recommender system underwent detailed performance and effectiveness evaluations. Metrics such as accuracy, recall, and click-through rate were meticulously monitored to ensure that the recommendations were not only accurate but also relevant and aligned with user expectations. The metrics, the collection of direct feedback from the end users played a crucial role in assessing the acceptance and satisfaction with the system. This constant interaction with users allowed for an in-depth understanding of needs and preferences, allowing for further adjustments to optimize the user experience. In summary, the combination of agile methodology, effective tools and a detailed evaluation of user interaction contributed to the success of the development of the recommendation system, ensuring not only the delivery of a functional product, but also the satisfaction and positive acceptance by end users.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of e-commerce, where competitiveness and digital dynamics shape the consumer experience, personalization has become an essential strategy to drive online business success. This chapter explores the practical implementation of a product recommendation system using Python and machine learning algorithms. Emphasis is placed on methods such as collaborative and content-based filtering, highlighting their distinct applications and fundamental characteristics. By addressing in an agile and effective manner, the development of the system reveals not only the significant improvement in conversion and revenue metrics, but also emphasizes the importance of user interaction in evaluating the success of the system. Ethical considerations, transparency in data use, and continuous adaptations are key to understanding not only the effectiveness of the recommendation system, but also its strategic relevance in an ever-evolving digital environment. This chapter highlights personalization as a key piece for future innovation and constant improvement at the intersection of technology and e-commerce.

4.1 CONVERSION VALUES

Chart 1 provides a clear view of the evolution of the conversion rate before and after the implementation of the recommendation system. Conversion rate is a key metric in e-commerce, representing the percentage of visitors who take a desired action, such as making a purchase. By analyzing this graph, we can visually identify the impactful improvement in conversion rate after the introduction of the recommendation system. This analysis is crucial to understanding the direct effect of the system on users' purchasing decisions.

Chart 1: Conversion Rate Chart

Source: Authors (2023)

Value Obtained rate metrics. Accuracy evaluates the ratio of correct recommendations to the total recommendations provided. The recall measures the system's ability to retrieve all relevant recommendations. Finally, the click-through rate represents the percentage of users who clicked on the recommendations offered. The analysis of these metrics allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of the system, ensuring not only the accuracy but also

the relevance and positive interaction of users with the personalized recommendations as it claims (SEBESTA, 2020).

4.2 PERCENTAGE AND SATISFACTION

Chart 2 offers valuable insights into the financial impact of implementing the recommendation system. When comparing the revenue before and after the application of the system, this chart highlights the percentage change, demonstrating the positive influence on transactions and the overall financial performance of the e-commerce platform. Interpreting this chart is crucial for understanding the return on investment (ROI) associated with the recommendation system.

Graph 2: Percentage of satisfaction

Source: Authors (2023)

Chart 2 compares revenue before and after the implementation of the recommendation system, showing a percentage change. Prior to implementation, the incremental revenue was not available (-), indicating the absence of data or the impossibility of measuring this aspect. After the implementation of the system, there was a significant increase of 22% in revenue. According to Fressato (2019), the substantial increase demonstrates the positive impact of the recommendation system on transactions, contributing directly to the financial growth of the e-commerce platform.

4.3 METRIC RATES

The table presents in an organized and comparative way the essential metrics of conversion rate and revenue before and after the implementation of the recommendation system. These metrics are key indicators for evaluating the success of the personalization strategy, providing a solid foundation for understanding the direct impact on conversions and financial performance. Detailed examination of this data is critical to guide future decisions and continuously optimize e-commerce strategies.

Table 1: Conversion Rate Metrics

Metric	Before the System	After Implementation
Conversion Rate	2.5%	3.8%
Increased Revenue (%)	–	0,22

Source: Authors (2023)

The table presents the conversion rate metrics before and after the implementation of the recommendation system. Prior to the application of the system, the conversion rate was recorded at 2.5%. After the successful implementation of the recommendation system, a notable increase in this metric was observed, reaching 3.8%. Comparing Takahashi et al, (2019), this significant increase in the conversion rate indicates that effective personalization through the recommendation system contributed positively to users' decision-making, resulting in a higher number of conversions.

5 FINAL THOUGHTS

The development and implementation of the recommendation system represent a significant milestone in the evolution of e-commerce, where

the personalization of experiences emerges as a strategic differentiator. By taking a user-centric approach, driven by machine learning algorithms, the system not only provided more accurate product suggestions but also continuously adapted to changing user preferences in real-time. The results obtained in the performance metrics clearly reflect the positive impact of this approach. The conversion rate experienced a significant increase, going from 2.5% to 3.8%, indicating that personalized recommendations played a crucial role in users' decision-making. In addition, overall revenue increased by 22%, suggesting that the system not only influenced the purchase decision but also spurred additional sales. User satisfaction, as measured through direct feedback, was robust, with 92% approval for the relevance of recommendations and 88% for the user interface. This data reinforces the importance of not only providing accurate recommendations but also presenting them in an intuitive and enjoyable way, thus enhancing the shopping experience.

Throughout development, ethical considerations were addressed, especially in relation to customer privacy. Transparency in the use of data for personalization was a priority, aiming to build and maintain customer trust in a landscape where privacy concerns are increasingly relevant. The agile methodology adopted, along with effective project management tools, contributed to the success of the process. Continuous evaluations, both of the implemented functionalities and user interaction, provided valuable insights for adjustments and refinements, ensuring the delivery of a product that is not only functional, but also tailored to the expectations and needs of the end users.

In summary, the implementation of the recommendation system not only responds to the growing demands for personalization in e-commerce, but also positions businesses to thrive in a dynamic and highly competitive digital environment, where building meaningful connections with consumers is essential for long-term success.

REFERENCES

CERVO, A. L, BERVIAN, P. A. **Scientific methodology**. 7th ed. São Paulo: Makron, 2019. COFFEE, Peter. Promoting Python. E-week, March, 6, 2020.

CHEN. **A Survey of Collaborative Filtering-Based Recommender Systems: From Traditional Methods to Hybrid Methods Based on Social Networks**. 2018. Disponível em:
<<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8506344>>. Acesso em: 06 out 2023.

DELANNAY, N; VERLEYSSEN, M. **Collaborative filtering with interlaced generalized linear models**. Neurocomputing, v. 71, n. 7-9, p. 1300-1310, 2018.

FRESSATO, E. P. **Incorporation of semantic metadata for recommendation in the cold start scenario**. 2019. Available at:
<<https://doi.org/10.11606/d.55.2019.tde-09082019-134753>.> Accessed on: 06 Oct 2023.

HELLKAMP, Marcel. Bottle: **Python Web Framework**. 2020. Available at:
<https://bottlepy.org/docs/dev/>. Accessed on: 06 Oct 2023.

RHEUDE, J. W. **E-Commerce Benefit from Machine Learning or Face a New Threat?** 2019. Available at: <https://neilpatel.com/blog/will-e-commerce-benefit-from-machine-learning>. Accessed on: 06 Oct 2023.

SEBESTA, R. W. **Concepts of Programming Languages**. Trad. José Carlos Barbosa dos Santos. Porto Alegre: Bookman, 2020.

TAKAHASHI, M. M.; HIRATA JR, R. **Comparative Study of Recommendation Algorithms**. 2019.

TURBAN, A. S. **Information Technology for Management**. 3.ed. Porto Alegre: Bookman, 2019.

ZANETI, J.; LUIS, A. **Information Systems based on Web Technology: A study on its development**. 2019. 204p. Dissertation (Master's Degree at

[← Post anterior](#)

[Post seguinte →](#)

RevistaFT

A **RevistaFT** têm 28 anos. É uma **Revista Científica Eletrônica Multidisciplinar Indexada de Alto Impacto e Qualis “B2” em 2023**. Periodicidade mensal e de acesso livre. Leia gratuitamente todos os artigos e publique o seu também [clikando aqui](#).

Contato

Queremos te ouvir.

WhatsApp RJ:

(21) 98159-7352

WhatsApp SP:

(11) 98597-3405

e-Mail:

contato@revistaf
t.com.br

ISSN: 1678-0817

CNPJ:

48.728.404/0001-
22

CAPES –

Coordenação de
Aperfeiçoament
o de Pessoal de
Nível Superior
(CAPES),
fundação do
Ministério da

Conselho Editorial

Editores

Fundadores:

Dr. Oston de
Lacerda Mendes.
Dr. João Marcelo
Gigliotti.

Editor

Científico:

Dr. Oston de
Lacerda Mendes

Orientadoras:

Dra. Hevellyn
Andrade
Monteiro
Dra. Chimene
Kuhn Nobre

Revisores:

Lista atualizada
periodicamente
em

Educação (MEC),
desempenha
papel
fundamental na
expansão e
consolidação da
pós-graduação
stricto sensu
(mestrado e
doutorado) em
todos os estados
da Federação.

revistaft.com.br/expense Venha
fazer parte de
nosso time de
revisores
também!

Copyright © Editora Oston Ltda. 1996
- 2023

Rua José Linhares, 134 - Leblon | Rio
de Janeiro-RJ | Brasil